

JURISPRUDENCE

THE CONCEPT OF A SENTENCE IN A CRIMINAL PROCESS

Airapetean A.

*PhD in Law, associate professor,
University of European Studies of Moldova*

Abstract

In the science of criminal procedure law, it is generally recognized that the sentence is an act of justice. However, in legislation and in theory, the concept of a sentence is defined in different ways, often to such an extent briefly that it does not reveal its main properties as an act of justice. If, from the point of view of the wording contained in the criminal procedural legislation, such an approach to the definition of the concept of a sentence is quite understandable and explainable (after all, first of all, the legal norm is of a general nature, impersonal, typical and cannot cover all possible situations that appear in life¹) then it is hardly justified from a scientific standpoint. This necessitates the need to formulate such a concept of a sentence in the modern criminal process, which would reflect its features as fully as possible.

Keywords: criminal procedural legislation, criminal procedure law, act of justice, criminal process.

Many of them have been and remain the subject of scientific research. They are thoroughly and deeply developed in the theory of criminal procedure law. However, with regard to others, it is impossible to speak so categorically. This conclusion is led by an analysis of the relevant norms of the criminal procedural legislation and the definitions of the concept of a sentence formulated in science. In the criminal procedure codes of most countries of the post-Soviet space, the term "sentence" is defined as a decision made by the court in a meeting on the guilt or innocence of the defendant and on the application or non-application of punishment to him².

Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova, para) 42 Art. 6 clarifies the term "sentence" somewhat differently, in particular as "a decision rendered by a court of first instance in a case considered on the merits". Note that the legislator is trying to get away from the definition of the sentence formulated in theory in the question of guilt. This happened due to the fact that in the current legislation there appeared such types of sentences as "sentence to terminate the proceedings", "sentence to apply coercive medical measures", "sentence to terminate the proceedings to apply coercive medical measures", "sentence on the rejection of the application for revision of the case in an audit procedure" and "the verdict in the case of a plea agreement".

An analysis of the theoretical provisions explaining the term "sentence" allows us to identify the main features that play a decisive role in formulating the concept of a sentence as an act of justice in criminal cases. So, a sentence is a decision made by the court of first instance in a court session, giving answers to questions about the presence or absence of a crime, the guilt or innocence of persons sent to the court, about the type

and amount of punishment, if guilt is established by the court.

It is impossible not to notice that even such a generalized description of the elements of the sentence, relating to the concept of it as an act of justice, although contradicting the current legislation, only expands the possibilities of formulating a more complete definition, but does not exhaust them. It should not be ignored that, along with the growth of the number of norms, the number of contradictions between them also grows³. Thus, with the advent of new types of sentences in the current criminal procedural structure, the definition of the sentence has undergone significant changes.

There are other very important signs of the sentence, developed by science, which should certainly be included in the definition. So, for example, in all legislative definitions there is no indication that the sentence is passed in the name of the law. Revealing the essence and meaning of the sentence as an act of justice, some authors emphasize that it is pronounced in the name of the law⁴, moreover, one of the features of the sentence is expressed in the named sign. What is the reason that this important and essential feature is not included in the legislative definition of a sentence? It is clear that this gap needs to be filled.

Crime, as the most dangerous type of offense, causes socially dangerous harm to the individual, his rights and freedoms, property, environment, constitutional order, sovereignty, independence and territorial integrity of the Republic of Moldova, peace, security humanity, and the entire legal order. In the system of guarantees of human rights and freedoms, an important place is occupied by the criminal law protection of

¹ E. Arama. The rule of law and the discretionary power of the judge // National Journal of Law, no. 10, 2003, p. 17.

² Iu. Sedletsky. The concept and main features of an acquittal// Scientific annals of the State University of Moldova, No. 5, 2001, p. 313.

³ E. Arama. The rule of law and the discretionary power of the judge // National Journal of Law, no. 10, 2003, p. 17.

⁴ A. Borodac, M. Gherman. Criminal liability // Law and Life, no. 11, 2005, p. 5-6.

these values⁵. It is quite clear that it is the criminal law that is given such a high "honor" as the protection of the above values from criminal encroachments. And that is why the verdicts of the courts of the Republic of Moldova, which represent the final stage of the consideration of the case in court, are issued in the name of the law.

We believe that under the passing of a sentence "in the name of the law" (part (2) of Article 384 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova), the supremacy of the law is assumed when the respective court decision is passed. No one can be accused of committing a crime, and no one can be subjected to criminal punishment except on the basis of a final decision of the court, issued in accordance with the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova. Justice in criminal cases is carried out in the name of the law only by the courts. The creation of illegal courts is prohibited. Sentences and other judicial decisions issued by illegally established courts have no legal force and are not enforceable (art. 25 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova). The courts of the Republic of Moldova, formed in accordance with the current legislation, not only have this right, i.e. the right to judge, but, and the obligation to administer justice in the name of the law.

However, being an imperious act, the verdict of the court does not create the norms of law. It has an individual, law enforcement character. By its legal nature, a court verdict, like other decisions in a criminal process, is an act of applying the rule of law to specific legal relations. In the light of the above positions, it is impossible not to point out another equally important provision known in the criminal procedural literature as the presumption of innocence. After all, it seems to us that this provision contributes to the passing of a just sentence, and only such a sentence can be passed in the name of the law.

The presumption of innocence in criminal proceedings plays the role of an important guarantee against unreasonable conviction of a person who is innocent of a crime, and at the same time is one of the important conditions that ensure the discovery of material truth in a criminal case⁶. "Any person accused of committing a crime is considered innocent until his guilt is established by law through a public trial, in which he is provided with all the necessary guarantees for his defense" - this provision of Article 21 of the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova is duplicated by Article 8 Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova, for some inconsistency in details.

The presumption of innocence implies the need to establish guilt in a legal manner, and confirmation of this very guilt in accordance with the definition provided for in Article 8 of the Code of Criminal Procedure is carried out by a final judgment of conviction. Yes, but after all, the current structure of the criminal procedure law also provides for such sentences as "a sentence

in the case of a plea agreement", "a sentence to terminate the proceedings" on some grounds, according to which a person is found guilty, but in relation to him not a guilty verdict. Does this imply a contradiction with the principle of the presumption of innocence declared in the criminal procedure law? Certainly yes. Indeed, regardless of which of these sentences the court decides, it is necessary to prove the guilt of the defendant. The Procrustean bed of this issue boils down to the fact that all the activities of the courts in issuing sentences, in which it is necessary to establish the guilt of the defendant with a ruling different from the guilty verdict, contradicts the basic principle of the criminal process - the presumption of innocence. These contradictions urgently need to be brought into line.

All activities of the authorities preceding the sentencing criminal prosecution, the prosecutor's office and the court is necessary only for the court to pass a sentence in full accordance with the current legislation, i.e. in the name and in the name of the rule of law. The purpose of the criminal process - establishing the truth in a criminal case, exposing and punishing the person who committed the crime, and protecting an innocent person from unfounded accusation and conviction - is achieved when a court decides a just sentence.

One cannot but agree that this goal is achieved only in the case of exact observance of the law⁷. After all, only then can one speak of an increased preventive effect of the sentence, since it demonstrates the potential threat of coercion contained in the law as a real measure of punishment for a specific person for a committed criminal act. Let us assume that an unlawful and unreasonable sentence has been passed in the case. This entails a number of negative consequences: from violating the legitimate interests of the participants in the process and ending with the undermining of the authority of the judiciary and the formation of a disrespectful attitude towards the law in society.

The current legislation of the Russian Federation has accepted the previously effective provision on passing a sentence "in the name of the state" and, as it seems to us, is not unreasonable. Processualists give a huge number of arguments to justify this position. Among the arguments, one should highlight the importance of the verdict as an act of the state, because the court administers justice on behalf of the state, because, endowed with this right - the state. This is also explained by the fact that in the verdict the state expresses its attitude to the actions considered in the court session and to the person who committed them. The passing of a sentence in the name of the state also means that the enforcement of the sentence is ensured by the power of state power.

In Article 269 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova of 1961, the phrase "in the name of the Republic of Moldova" was changed by Law no. 809 of 10.04.96 to the phrase "in the name of

⁵ V. Stati. Offenses against the political, labor and other constitutional rights of citizens // National Law Review, no. 3, 2005, p. 11.

⁶ Yu. Sedletsky. Acquittal and its socio-political significance//Dissertation for the degree of candidate of legal sciences. M., 1988, Chapter III, p. 5.

⁷ Gh. Golubenco. The object and system of forensics: current problems // Law and Life, no. 10, 2005, p. 4.

the law". Republic - "public cause"⁸ (translated from Latin: res - business, publicus - society) - the sentence was supposed to be passed in the name of "public cause", and not the law, and this is essential. Everyone makes mistakes: people, political parties, groups, peoples. Only the law cannot be mistaken, if this law is the experience of generations, and not a faceless collection of faceless provisions, forgetting about the sovereign power - the people, and after all, the people are the source of all the power that the state has⁹.

We believe that it was these grounds that were taken by the legislator for granted, which resulted in their legislative consolidation in part (2) of Art. 384 Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova. The verdict will lose its quality if it is seen only as a means of resolving the accusation on the merits. Namely, the appointment of the sentence Fatkullin F¹⁰ and Nadi L¹¹. More successfully, but contradictory, the essence of the sentence is determined by Malikov M¹². He writes: "The only means of resolving the accusation and the case as a whole is a court verdict."

The verdict is the result of all the procedural activities preceding the issuance of it, as Yu. Grosheva¹³ rightly notes. Kutsova E¹⁴. he connects the legality and validity of the sentence with the observance of the norms of criminal and criminal procedural law during the investigation and consideration of criminal cases, that is, with all procedural activities. Lupinskaya P¹⁵. Also draws attention to the fact that "the legality and validity of the sentence largely depend on the legality and validity of those decisions that are made on various issues in the course of the proceedings." "All the actions of the preliminary investigation bodies, the prosecutor's office and the court that precede the verdict are ultimately aimed at ensuring the conditions necessary for issuing the correct verdict," writes Alpert S¹⁶. The statement of M. Strogovich¹⁷ is also very interesting, asserting that "The decision by the court of the verdict completes the previous stages of criminal proceedings: the initiation of a criminal case and its investigation (inquiry and preliminary investigation), trial." Davydov P. unequivocally and clearly states that the verdict sums up not only the trial, but the entire proceedings. However, there is another point of view on the issue under consideration, which is shared by a number of proceduralists. So, Ageeva G¹⁸. believes that the sentencing sums up the outcome of the case in court. With such an interpretation, it remains incomprehensible and inexplicable whether the materials of the criminal prosecution bodies have any significance for the formation of the verdict.

In 1869, Judicial reform was carried out in Bessarabia. According to the Charter of Criminal Proceedings, by listening to the parties and by analyzing all the evidence available in the case, the justice of the peace decided on the guilt or innocence of the defendant.¹⁹ It was not by chance that we offered a brief excursion into the history of the criminal procedure legislation of our state. This was done in order to show the fact of resolving the issue regarding the guilt of the defendant in the sentencing.

We believe that in the criminal procedure legislation the definition of a sentence should be fixed in the following form: "A sentence is an act of justice pronounced in the name of the law by a court of first instance, adopted as a result of a trial on all issues of a criminal case - on the guilt of the defendant and his punishment or release from punishment, or from serving a sentence, or on release from criminal liability; on the application of compulsory medical measures; on the innocence and acquittal of the defendant; on the termination of proceedings in the case - as well as on all issues related to the decision of the verdict - on a civil suit, a preventive measure, the fate of material evidence, court costs and others specified in Art. 385 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova".

References

1. Borodac, M. Gherman. Criminal liability // Law and Life, no. 11, 2005, p. 5-6.
2. Borshevsky. Characteristics of the decision and announcement of sentences in the criminal process by the justices of the peace of Bessarabia (late 60s-70s of the XIX century) // Law and Life, No. 9, 2005, p. 52.
3. Big encyclopedic dictionary. SPb., 1998, p. 1013; see also: New encyclopedic dictionary. M, 2000, p. 1022.
4. Arama. The rule of law and the discretionary power of the judge // National Journal of Law, no. 10, 2003, p. 17.
5. Kutsova. Verdict, M., 1962, p. 6.
6. Fatkullin. Charge and court verdict, Kazan, 1965, p. 88.
7. Ageeva. The verdict of the Soviet court - an act of socialist justice, M., 1957, p. 9.
8. Kostaki, E. Denchuk. Democratic principles of the modern Constitution // Law and Life, No. 7, 2004, p. 11.
9. Gh. Golubenco. The object and system of forensic: current problems // Law and Life, no. 10, 2005, p. 4.

⁸ Big encyclopedic dictionary. SPb., 1998, p. 1013; see also: New encyclopedic dictionary. M, 2000, p. 1022.

⁹ G. Kostaki, E. Denchuk. Democratic principles of the modern Constitution // Law and Life, No. 7, 2004, p. 11.

¹⁰ F. Fatkullin. Charge and court verdict, Kazan, 1965, p. 88.

¹¹ L. Nadi. Verdict in the criminal process, M., 1982, p. 123.

¹² M. Malikov. Problems of the court verdict, Ufa, 1987, p. 28.

¹³ Yu. Grosheva. Legal properties of the sentence - an act of socialist justice, Kharkov, 1978, p. 13.

¹⁴ E. Kutsova. Verdict, M., 1962, p. 6.

¹⁵ P. Lupinskaya. Decisions in criminal proceedings, M., 1976, p. 71.

¹⁶ S. Alpert. Resolution of the verdict // Soviet criminal process, Kyiv, 1983, p. 49.

¹⁷ M. Strogovich. The ratio of the preliminary investigation and trial, and some questions of defense in the Soviet criminal process, L., 1967, p. 103.

¹⁸ G. Ageeva. The verdict of the Soviet court - an act of socialist justice, M., 1957, p. 9.

¹⁹ A. Borshevsky. Characteristics of the decision and announcement of sentences in the criminal process by the justices of the peace of Bessarabia (late 60s-70s of the XIX century) // Law and Life, No. 9, 2005, p. 52.

10. Iu. Sedletsy. The concept and main features of an acquittal// Scientific annals of the State University of Moldova, No. 5, 2001, p. 313.
11. Nadi. Verdict in the criminal process, M., 1982, p. 123.
12. Malikov. Problems of the court verdict, Ufa, 1987, p. 28.
13. Strogovich. The ratio of the preliminary investigation and trial, and some questions of defense in the Soviet criminal process, L., 1967, p. 103.
14. P. Lupinskaya. Decisions in criminal proceedings, M., 1976, p. 71.
15. S. Alpert. Resolution of the verdict // Soviet criminal process, Kyiv, 1983, p. 49.
16. V. Stati. Offenses against the political, labor and other constitutional rights of citizens // National Law Review, no. 3, 2005, p. 11.
17. Yu. Grosheva. Legal properties of the sentence - an act of socialist justice, Kharkov, 1978, p. 13.
18. Yu. Sedletsy. Acquittal and its socio-political significance//Dissertation for the degree of candidate of legal sciences. M., 1988, Chapter III, p. 5.